

AGROBANK LOANING OF INVESTMENT PROJECTS

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Abstract In the context of the development of the national economy, their modeling through the regulation of investment activities in commercial banks requires improvement. In particular, banks are pursuing a soft monetary policy to ensure liquidity, and their troubled assets are being purchased. Also, under the influence of the pandemic, investment projects financed by commercial banks remain ineffective.

Keywords: Commercial banking, investment activities, credit, financing.

Introduction In the context of globalization, the economy requires the satisfaction of infinite needs on the basis of limited resources. Lending of investment projects by commercial banks and their effective use are ways to increase the level of sustainable development of the economy.

In his address to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev said, “First of all, we must create an effective system for attracting foreign loans and investments, learn to use each loan accurately. The time has come to work on this issue, to measure seven times, to cut once, and to think carefully about the consequences. ”

The Action Strategy for the Development of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 sets the task of increasing the volume of lending to economic and investment projects by 1.2 times, expanding the scope of financial support for family businesses and crafts in order to modernize and expand production by commercial banks. This, in turn,

means improving the banking system, increasing the level of capitalization and reforming.

Among transnational investment institutions, the World Bank Group is the group that, along with the IMF, has a significant impact on the direction of economic development and growth in most countries. This group coordinates the economic assistance policies of industrialized countries, influences the activities of other international economic organizations, and provides practical assistance to developing countries in developing economic development programs.

Foreign credit accelerates the process of reproduction through the following directions.

First, credit stimulates the country's foreign economic relations, thereby creating a demand that boosts market conditions. At present, the share of "dependency" loans, which are exported from the creditor country, has increased. The cost of purchasing government goods on credit is a credit condition. In the same way, a foreign loan serves to increase the competitiveness of the country's enterprises.

Second, foreign credit creates a favorable environment for foreign private investment, usually with the obligation to provide incentives to foreign investors. The establishment of infrastructure, including the operation of foreign and joint ventures, will strengthen the position of national enterprises and banks with international capital.

Third, credit ensures the continuity of international settlements and foreign exchange transactions that serve the country's foreign economic relations.

Fourth, credit increases the economic efficiency of the country's foreign trade operations and stimulates the development of other types of foreign economic activity.

In particular, the lack of foreign currency resources in commercial banks to finance investment projects, or the low share of foreign currency loans for the purchase of equipment and technology from abroad, or their constant unsatisfied demand for foreign currency loans hinders the development of small businesses.

Currently, international financial institutions have a number of programs aimed at financing small businesses through commercial banks in the country.

**Figure 1. Foreign currency loans provided by Agrobank for 2010-2018
(in thousands of US dollars)**

According to Figure, in 2017, Agrobank's branches issued 14.5 million soums in foreign currency. In the first 5 months of 2018, the figure was 27.9 million US dollars. USD or 1.9 times more than last year and 2.4 times more than in 2014. Loans in foreign currency were made at the expense of foreign credit lines and Agrobank's own foreign currency.

In order to communicate directly with international financial institutions and foreign banks, commercial banks are required to have a high rating, financial stability, a foothold in the financial market and a modern management system.

The role and place of individual sources in financing investment projects is largely determined by macroeconomic balance and growth stability, the level of development and interrelationships of forms of ownership, the development of the banking and financial system and other factors.

Conclusion World experience shows that the integration of the national economy into the world economy and the targeted use of the opportunities of the international division of labor cannot be ensured without creating a favorable investment climate. The investment climate depends on the country's existing natural, economic and labor resources, macroeconomic policy, institutional conditions and other factors. Many economically developed countries, which have such conditions, are interested in attracting loans from international and foreign financial institutions. In addition, the essence of international financial institutions is to provide financial assistance to member states. Therefore, it provides financial assistance to developing and transition countries and provides them with external financial resources. The allocation of loans by international financial institutions and foreign banks to our country contributes to the development of our financial market, large-scale financing of small businesses. there is no doubt that getting a loan from financial institutions at reasonable interest rates is a convenient tool.

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